

August 2022: Top 5 Cited Articles in Microwave Engineering

International Journal of Microwave
Engineering (JMICO)

ISSN : 2455 - 7870

<https://airccse.com/jmicro/index.html>

Cited by

	All	Since 2017
Citations	25	25
h-index	3	3
i10-index	0	0

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=tR55NdkAAAAJ>

STUDY OF ABSORPTION IN CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITES FROM 1HZ TO 40GHZ

Aline Emplit and Isabelle Huynen

Institute of Communication Technologies, Electronics and Applied Mathematics (ICTEAM),
Université catholique de Louvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium

ABSTRACT

Absorption performances in High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) and polycarbonate (PC) polymer matrices containing various loads of carbon nanotubes were analysed. It depends on electrical conductivity, dielectric constant and thickness of the polymer composites. These parameters can be easily controlled. Significant absorption, which can reach between 60 and 90%, hence occurs at particular combinations of these last parameters (in a frequency range from 1Hz to GHz). These new results are really useful in various applications, and are considered in low scale systems as a major technological solution against electromagnetic interferences.

KEYWORDS

Microwave absorbers, electromagnetic interferences, nanocomposites, carbon nanotubes

Full Text: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/papers/2117jmicro01.pdf>

Volume URL: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/vol2.html>

ESTIMATING THE TARGET TRACKING USING A SET OF RANGE – PARAMETERS FOR GAIN MODIFICATION USING KALMAN FILTERS

P.Devi Pradeep, D.Arun Kumar & G.Sahu

***Assistant Professor, Department of ECE, GMRIT, RAJAM, AP, INDIA**

ABSTRACT

Bearings-only tracking using the modified gain extended Kalman filter (MGEKF) configured in Cartesian coordinate systems is reviewed. A new tracking approach is proposed which consists of a set of weighted MGEKFs each with a different initial range estimate and this is referred to as the range-parameterized (RP) tracker. This new approach overcomes the problems exhibited with existing MGEKF trackers.

Results are presented for a typical tracking scenario, involving a manoeuvring observer and a constant velocity target. The results show that the RP tracker gives stable, consistent and unbiased estimates in all the cases considered. Although only constant velocity target trajectories have been considered in this paper, the RP tracker provides a natural framework for consideration of manoeuvring targets.

Full Text: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/papers/1116jmicro01.pdf>

Volume URL: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/vol1.html>

DESIGN OF PRINTED MONOPOLE ANTENNA FOR MICROWAVE COMMUNICATION

Yogesh B. Thakare¹

**1 Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, PVG's COET
(Affiliated to University of Pune), Pune-09 (INDIA).**

ABSTRACT

A printed monopole in its planar and vertical configuration has been designed, fabricated and analyzed for microwave applications on low cost FR4 substrate material of thickness, $h = 1.56$ mm and relative permittivity, $\epsilon_r = 4.3$. The designed planar monopole has been simulated and experimented to find its frequency response with coplanar waveguide feed to exhibit dual band characteristics with -10 dB reflection loss bandwidth of 45.078 % (i.e. 1.5:1 between 1.334 and 2.109 GHz) and 114.92 % (i.e. 3.7: 1 between 3.99 and 14.77 GHz). The vertical monopole using the same patch has also been simulated and experimented and -10 dB reflection loss bandwidth of 173.67% (14.2:1 between 0.925 and 13.125 GHz) has been obtained. The antenna finds many applications in microwave bands.

KEYWORDS

Antenna, Fractal, Monopole, Microwave, UWB.

Full Text: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/papers/1416jmicro05.pdf>

Volume URL: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/vol1.html>

A NEW HYBRID METHOD FOR SYNTHETIC APERTURE RADAR DECEPTIVE JAMMING

**Jamal Saeedi Electrical Engineering Department, Amirkabir University of Technology,
Tehran, Iran**

ABSTRACT

Based on the synthetic aperture radar (SAR) geometric model, a novel, and fast algorithm of large scene deceptive jamming against different SAR systems is proposed. First, a template deceptive image is transformed into the time domain signal using inverse image formation algorithm. Then, the transformed signal is convolved with enemy's received SAR signal in order to cope with electronic countercountermeasures (ECCM) techniques. Finally, the generated jamming signal is transmitted to enemy's SAR system for deceptive purpose. Specifically, we have proposed a hybrid method for SAR jamming, which uses a digital radio frequency memory (DRFM) system incorporating with SAR raw data simulation module. The experimental results for the proposed deceptive jammer demonstrate its ability to deceive SAR system.

KEYWORDS

Synthetic aperture radar; deceptive jamming; digital radio frequency memory; SAR raw data simulation.

Full Text: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/papers/4119jmicro01.pdf>

Volume URL: https://airccse.com/jmicro/vol4_jmicro.html

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT SYMMETRIC SLITS ON MICROSTRIP PATCH ANTENNA

Suvidya Pawar¹ , R. Sreemathy² and Shahadev Hake³

¹²³Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Pune Institute of Computer Technology, affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, India

ABSTRACT

In this paper, a basic linearly polarised microstrip square patch antenna operating at 2.4 GHz is proposed. We have modified the basic microstrip square patch antenna with rectangular shape slits, V shape slits and truncated corners to achieve circular polarization. Basically we have designed five different antennas to meet the specification. The various antennas have been simulated, fabricated and the performance has been tested on network analyser (Agilent Technologies: N9912A, SNMY51464189, ROHDE & SCHWARZ: ZVL13, 9 KHz to 13.6GHz.). The simulated and tested performance shows close agreement with each other. The various structures used in this study are microstrip square patch radiator, microstrip square patch radiator with truncated corner, rectangular slits, truncated corner with rectangular slits and V shape slits. The experiment results show rectangular slits with truncated corners in the main square patch and rectangular slits in the main square patch provide better performance with respect to the antenna parameters. Designed antenna is compact and provides circular polarization at the required operating frequency of 2.4GHz with improved bandwidth and gain. The use of circularly polarized antennas presents an attractive solution to achieve this polarization match which allows for more flexibility in the angle between transmitting and receiving antennas. It gives the following advantages such as reduction in the effect of multipath reflections, decrease in transmission losses, enhancement of weather penetration and allowing any orientation to the communication system.

KEYWORDS

Wireless, microstrip antenna, circular polarization, slit

Full Text: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/papers/1416jmicro03.pdf>

Volume URL: <https://airccse.com/jmicro/vol1.html>